

POLICY BRIEF

Co-UDlabs
COLLABORATIVE URBAN DRAINAGE
RESEARCH LABS COMMUNITIES

Assessing CSO spills

Summary

Sewage discharges from Combined Sewer Overflow (CSO) structures into receiving waters can prevent floods in urban areas but can also harm ecosystems and public health. In many countries there is a lack of reliable data on their operational frequency and pollution loads released. Assessing the impact of CSOs is challenging, emission-based rules that focus on the number of spills per year are insufficient to quantify environmental harm and lack of continuous information on the receiving water makes impact-based regulations hard to enforce.

From Co-UDlabs we recommend further research on environmental and human impacts of intermittent CSO spills, operational improvements to eliminate dry-weather spills, integrated CSO impact evaluation with wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) discharges, and targeting stormwater inflows by promoting Nature Based Solutions. Climate change and hydrological signature modifications must be considered for instance by performing projections of future rainfall patterns or river flows and changes in land uses. We recommend supporting the recast of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD) with monitoring technology development projects involving large Research Infrastructures and see substantial business opportunities in CSO monitoring innovations. We also recommend funding to enable the sharing of monitoring experience between all water utilities to share learning. Raising awareness of CSOs and sewerage systems will increase public support for infrastructure investment to mitigate flooding, environmental impacts and public health.

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Description of the problem

Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) are a necessary component of integrated Urban Drainage Systems

Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) act as relief valves in combined sewer systems, preventing sewage from flooding into streets and homes during heavy rainfall. CSOs also prevent wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) malfunction during wet weather as biological treatment process can be affected during heavy rainfall scenarios. Their design allows regulators to specify acceptable flood risk, public health and environmental impacts on aquatic systems. CSOs allow for a single pipe network for both sewage and stormwater, reducing infrastructure costs especially in older urban areas, where retrofitting a completely separated system is often impractical and expensive. However, due to changes in rainfall runoff patterns caused by climate change and increased urbanization, CSO volumes are likely to increase over the long-term.

Impact of CSO spills on Environmental and Public Health

While CSOs are necessary, there is a growing concern about the impact of CSO spills on environment and public health. CSOs intermittently discharge untreated sewage into natural receiving water bodies, which introduces pollutants such as organic matter, nutrients, and pathogens, temporarily degrading water quality and potentially harming aquatic ecosystems. CSO discharges can also release stormwater from urban areas with a continuously increasing range of emerging contaminants of concern such as microplastics and pharmaceuticals and antimicrobial resistant pathogens from wastewater, posing new risks to the environment and human health. Water utilities often prioritize improving WWTPs and maintaining good wastewater treatment works effluent, which can lead to CSOs operating more frequently than required for overall drainage efficiency. Thus, reducing polluted urban stormwater and untreated wastewater discharges through CSOs is crucial to improve biodiversity in natural water bodies.

CSO design practice has evolved over time and compliance assessment with current regulations is challenging

The design of CSO structures has evolved over time, from simple “rules-of-thumb» guidance to more

complex guidance around emissions and receiving water impact. Traditional design has focused on prevention of sewage flooding streets and properties, and prevention of overloading WWTPs during heavy rain without consensus on the definition of a heavy rain. In recent decades, the focus has included reducing negative receiving water impacts from CSO spills whilst minimizing the flood risk and maximizing the WWTP benefits. However, assessing the impact of CSO spills on the receiving water is complex, as is tracing the source of pollution: it can originate from different sources, and the processes that transport and transform pollutants are naturally variable. This complexity makes it difficult to enforce regulations. Simple emission-based regulations such as spill frequency are easy to compare against collected data, but this does not provide knowledge about receiving water impact. Conversely, compliance with impact-based regulations is expensive and difficult to enforce, as the models and data collection schemes needed for this are complex. Operators often consider their job done when infrastructure has been constructed according to valid design standards. Monitoring CSOs, however, has not been a standard in many European areas, and where monitoring has happened the data has often been unreliable due to technical and non-technical issues. There is a need for a better understanding of how best to monitor CSO performance for regulation and compliance monitoring.

Left: Example of a non-functional CSO tank. The sticker says: “IMPORTANT! The red screw has to be removed after transport, otherwise no function”.

Bottom: CSO with traces of toilet paper in the vicinity.

Lack of consistent CSO performance data and regulatory scrutiny

In many countries, the exact number and location of CSOs are not known, and legally binding CSO emissions regulations do not exist. For instance, in England and Wales alone 14,530 CSO structures have been identified, but a large number of EU countries do not have official statistics readily available. It is almost impossible to know, at this time, the number of CSO structures and spills at European level¹. Many regions are struggling to implement a multitude of local regulations and guidelines around managing CSO performance, which has led to a variety of approaches. Collecting and interpreting performance data is costly and requires informed analysis from knowledgeable staff. This makes it difficult to assess the overall effectiveness of CSO management in Europe. The open publication of relatively simple CSO spill frequency data in England and Wales² has highlighted the measured number and duration of CSO spills at a national scale. The frequency and duration of spills was far larger than expected, pointing to a mismatch between expected performance derived from what were thought to be conservative model- and design-based approaches and actual performance. Furthermore, data reliability has been questionable: for instance, only 38% of data reported to German regional regulators were deemed plausible³. Far more resources ought to be devoted to

data quality improvement and monitoring³. The recent issue of bathing water quality in the Seine River during the 2024 Paris Olympics and the media spotlight on public CSO discharges database in England, moreover, have brought CSOs even more under public scrutiny.

Economic Factors also play a role

There is a need to balance the costs of CSO upgrades with the need to manage flood risk, protect the environment and public health. The cost of reducing CSO spills can impact citizens' water bills and carbon emissions, which leads to ongoing discussions about the management of water utilities. Large investments⁴ are expected to future-proof decaying urban drainage systems, making it important to understand where and how to invest to minimize the impacts.

¹ Schellart, A., Sharp, L., Bertrand-Krajewski, J.-L., Rieckerman, J. "The role of open data in regulating Combined Sewer Overflows". 16th International Conference on Urban Drainage, Jun 2024, Delft, Netherlands.

² <https://environment.data.gov.uk/dataset/21e15f12-0df8-4bfc-b763-45226c16a8ac>.

³ Dittmer, U., P. Alber, C. Seller, and W. Lieb. "Kenngrößen Für Die Bewertung Des Betriebes von Regenüberlaufbecken," 2015.

⁴ UK government stormwater overflow reduction plan has an estimated cost of 50.600 Mio € to meet spill reduction, public health and environmental targets. [UK - Storm overflows discharge reduction plan: Impact assessment \(2023\)](#).

Relevance to Legislation

CSO spills are a major environmental concern in the EU due to their impact on water quality, public health, and biodiversity. The EU is tightening regulations to enhance monitoring, improve urban drainage system planning, and minimizing overflows to support climate resilience, biodiversity conservation and pollution reduction goals.

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The Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)

mandates "good ecological and chemical status" in water bodies. Stormwater runoff and CSOs contribute to nutrient pollution, organic matter and micropollutants, hindering WFD compliance.

The Bathing Water Directive (2006/7/EC)

sets microbiological standards for recreational waters, requiring action against pathogen contamination from CSOs.

The Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (2024/3019)

mandates integrated wastewater management for large urban areas, stricter monitoring, and improved stormwater control using optimized infrastructure, nature-based solutions, and digital tools.

Policy Challenges

Addressing CSO is complex due to inconsistencies in regulation, lack of evidence, and additional institutional barriers. Despite their environmental impact, a clear understanding of CSO pollution remains difficult to achieve.

- Measuring CSO impact is not easy.** CSO pollution varies with rainfall patterns and determining the impact of intermittent discharges on public health and water ecology is a complex task. Comparing CSO emissions with WWTP discharges is challenging due to the different nature of the spills.
- Weak Regulations and Enforcement.** Many EU countries lack legally binding CSO limits, and compliance monitoring is inconsistent. Regulations often focus on spills frequency rather than their environmental impact, with no standardized way to assess pollution effects. There is a lack of incentives and common operators' culture for integrated stormwater planning and monitoring approaches.
- Data Gaps and Monitoring Challenges.** CSO monitoring is limited, with poor data quality and restricted public access. Estimating overflow volume, pollution loads, or toxicity is difficult, and existing data is often siloed, reducing public transparency. Results from the survey conducted by Co-UDlabs on monitoring CSO at EU level indicate, for example, that a large fraction of utilities are already monitoring the performance of their urban drainage systems. Unfortunately, this measurement data is mainly collected for operational optimization and is neither used as a basis for decision-making nor is it forwarded to authorities for performance monitoring or shared with the public.
- A Complex and Fragmented System.** Classifying and comparing CSO events is difficult due to continuous overflows' nature and the inconsistent methods used to define what a CSO spill is. National differences in CSO design and governance further complicate policy application. Existing administrative and institutional structures can lead to "data siloing", where data is isolated within individual organizations. This makes it difficult to combine data from different sources, e.g., rainfall, CSOs, WWTP performance, river flows and quality, which can reduce the value of the data. Additionally, wastewater plants lack incentives to accept stormwater, as it raises costs and disrupts operations.
- Institutional Barriers and Resistance to Change.** Beyond technical challenges, utilities and regulators often lack funding, IT expertise, and skilled personnel. Resistance to digital transformation and reliance on outdated methods is just slowly being overcome. Administrative fragmentation makes data sharing difficult, as different agencies store information in isolated formats. Political resistance to stricter regulations also hinders reform.
- The Path Forward.** Balancing infrastructure costs with environmental protection requires stronger regulations, better data sharing, revisiting the economic value of aquatic ecosystems and integrated decision-making. Digital tools, nature-based solutions, and transparent reporting can help, but real progress depends on commitment from policymakers, utilities, and the public.

Policy Recommendations

- Balance CSO emission-based standards and environmental quality standards to ensure environmental protection and public health compliance. Emission standards like CSO spill annual pollution loads provide clear compliance targets, but they do not adequately consider regional variability and not always guarantee water quality objectives as they do not account, for example, for acute impacts. Environmental quality standards focus on water quality. This has encouraged integrated stormwater planning which includes Urban Drainage Systems, WWTP, and potentially also industrial spills and agriculture diffuse pollution. This approach, however, complicates compliance assessment. A hybrid approach — one which combines emission standards with a pressure-sensitivity impact assessment for large urban agglomerations and sensitivity aquatic ecosystems — could promote regulatory clarity and cost-effective investment.
- Make CSO performance data publicly available with unified data descriptors and commons licenses, while also providing guidance on responsible data sharing, clear explanations, and collaboration with local citizen groups and communication experts. Public access to CSO and WWTP data through European Data Spaces would increase innovation, transparency, and smart governance. Digital platforms could be used to distribute common planning information, such as unified climate projections for rainfall and river flows. This would save resources, enable cross-country comparisons, and common approaches to infrastructure design.
- Enhance CSO monitoring by seeking skilled personnel in urban drainage and promoting the adoption of innovative sensors and procedures. Water utilities, stakeholders, and regulators personnel involved in CSO performance must be familiar with fundamental hydraulics and environmental processes occurring during wet weather flows, acknowledging how monitoring and modelling uncertainty may mask non-compliance and influence infrastructure design decisions and legal requirements. More innovation in this sector will make implementation of new sensors for water quality and ecotoxicity easier. Multidisciplinary approaches combining data from field campaigns, modelling, and machine learning algorithms should also be incentivized. More investment in CSO monitoring technology and data analysis can increase the innovation capacity of the EU's wastewater industry altogether.
- Support effective implementation of the UWWTD at national level. This should be achieved by launching EU-wide regional case-study work on data-based CSO compliance assessment — as well as by engaging river basin authorities, utilities, citizen groups, and research infrastructures. Develop a specific funding program involving international and national associations of wastewater operators to share information on existing experiences and lessons learned and establish an appropriate level of investment for compliance monitoring — all consistent with the timeline of the renewed UWWTD and the new Europe-wide policy efforts in this field.

